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ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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Ключевые слова: эпилепсия, беременность, роды, эклампсия, тератогенез.

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HOMILADORLIK PAYTIDA EPILEPSIYA HAQIDA ZAMONAVIY QARASHLAR (ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI)

ANNOTATSIYA

Epilepsiya homiladorlik va tug'ilishga to'sqinlik qiladigan kasallik emas. Hujumlarni to'liq nazorat qilish bilan homiladorlik va tug'ilishning fiziologik jarayoni mumkin. Tug'ilgan chaqaloqni kuzatadigan epileptolog, umumiy amaliyot shifokori, ginekolog, genetika, akusher va pediatriya hisobga olish kerak bo'lgan bir qator omillar mavjud. Epilepsiya bilan og'rigan ayollarda bolali bo'lish qobiliyati umumiy aholiga nisbatan o'rtacha 2 baravar kamaydi. Bu ham ijtimoiy, ham organik sabablarga bog'liq. Antiepileptik dorilar (AEP) endokrin tizimning funktsiyalarini buzishi va jinsiy buzilishlar (gipo - yoki giperseksualizm), semirish, hipotiroidizm, polikistik tuxumdonlar, jinsiy rivojlanishning kechikishi, hayz ko'rish disfunktsiyasi va ovulyatsiya buzilishining rivojlanishiga olib kelishi mumkin. Maqolada epilepsiya bilan og'rigan homilador ayollarni boshqarish xususiyatlari muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: epilepsiya, homiladorlik, tug'ish, eklampsiya, teratogenez.

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CURRENT VIEWS ON EPILEPSY IN PREGNANCY

ANNOTATION

Epilepsy is not a condition that prevents pregnancy and childbirth. With complete control of seizures, a physiological pregnancy and delivery is possible. There are a number of factors that should be considered by the epileptologist, general practitioner, gynaecologist, geneticist, obstetrician and paediatrician who will observe the infant being born. The ability to have children in women with epilepsy is reduced on average by a factor of 2 compared to the general population. This is due to both social and organic causes. Antiepileptic drugs (AEDs) can disrupt the functions of the endocrine system and provoke the development of sexual disorders (hypo- or hypersexuality), obesity, hypothyroidism, polycystic ovaries, delayed sexual development, menstrual dysfunction and ovulation disorders. The article considers the peculiarities of management of pregnant women suffering from epilepsy.

Keywords: epilepsy, pregnancy, labour, eclampsia, teratogenesis.

Introduction. The onset of pregnancy in a woman with epilepsy is not only a desirable but also a very responsible stage of life. Therefore, it is necessary to explain to a patient of fertile age at her first visit to an epileptologist that this event, like any good impromptu pregnancy, should be planned.

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Pregnancy is contraindicated only in women with severe epilepsy, when AED administration does not allow avoiding frequent generalised

seizures, and in addition, the woman has pronounced psychiatric abnormalities.

Epilepsy is not a contraindication to IVF, although it should be remembered that to stimulate egg production, women candidates for IVF are given massive injections of hormones. This can sometimes provoke seizures.

Pregravidar preparation for women with epilepsy

Pregravidar (from Latin Gravidar - pregnant woman) preparation is a complex of preventive, diagnostic and therapeutic measures, the result of which is the readiness of future parents to fully conceive, carry and give birth to a healthy child. Planning a pregnancy is not just about taking vitamins, quitting drinking and smoking 1-2 months before conception. Pregravidarstvennaya preparation begins 6-10 months before the desired pregnancy and includes a certain list of procedures.

Pregravidarstvennaya preparation takes place in several stages:

Medical examination of the spouses.

Preparation of the couple to conceive, the woman - to carry the child.

Determination of favourable days for conception.

The number and volume of studies before the planned pregnancy are determined for each patient individually by the therapist, gynaecologist, geneticist. From the point of view of an epileptologist, it is necessary to determine the concentrations of AEDs in blood plasma; perform a general blood test with determination of the platelet level; biochemical blood test with determination of the level of ALT, AST, bilirubin, alkaline phosphatase; make an electroencephalogram (EEG) or perform video-EEG monitoring. In some cases, when planning pregnancy, it is advisable to conduct ultrasound examination of the uterus and its appendages, as well as a number of hormonal studies reflecting the function of the reproductive system of the woman. To select the dose of AEDs, regular study of the drug concentration in the blood is indicated, and to maintain a constant concentration it is desirable to use dosage forms with delayed release (durant forms).

The indication for unscheduled determination of AED concentration in blood before pregnancy is the increase/severity of attacks or the appearance of symptoms of intoxication.

In the pregravidar period, it is recommended to consult a geneticist to determine the risk of epilepsy in the future child. Epilepsy is not a hereditary disease, but in some cases it can be inherited. The risk of transmitting epilepsy to the child from the mother in genetic epilepsies is on average 10%, in unknown aetiology and structural epilepsy - 3%. The risk of passing epilepsy from the father averages 2.5%. If both parents suffer from epilepsy, the risk of the child inheriting epilepsy increases to 10-12%. If a woman suffers from structural or epilepsy of unknown aetiology, the risk for the future child increases threefold compared to the general population, in the case of genetic generalised or focal epilepsy - 10 times.

It is necessary to undergo genetic screening if:

both partners in a couple have epilepsy;

the couple already has a child with epilepsy;

one or both parents have a history of epilepsy, malformations (congenital cleft palate or "harelip", finger deformities, etc.) and hereditary diseases;

the patient has had 2 or more spontaneous miscarriages, fetal or neonatal deaths.

The main goal of the physician is to achieve complete control of the attacks before the desired pregnancy. An important indicator is the length of time the patient has been seizure-free before pregnancy: if she has been seizure-free for 9 months, there is a very high probability that she will be seizure-free during pregnancy. However, it is difficult to predict the course of each pregnancy.

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Features of management of pregnant women with epilepsy

For this period of life, the leading doctor is an obstetrician-gynaecologist, with whom the patient should be regularly observed. Up to 28 weeks. examinations are carried out 1 time per month, from 28 to 36 weeks - once every 2 weeks, and after 36 weeks. - every week. During the entire pregnancy a woman should be observed by an epileptologist: in case of complete control of seizures - once every 2 months, in case of recurrent partial seizures - once a month. The patient should be warned about the need to consult a doctor in case of increasing frequency of seizures. If there is any concomitant pathology: diabetes mellitus, anaemia, arterial hypertension, kidney disease, etc., - requires monitoring of related specialists. Most gynaecologists, neonatologists and paediatricians are very afraid of the negative effects of AEDs on the mother and foetus, but at the same time do not attach such importance to the drugs they prescribe. However, the prescription of AEDs is the competence of an epileptologist, and changes in the treatment regimen are possible only in agreement with him. If other specialists make adjustments in therapy or insist on the cancellation of AEDs, it is necessary to inform the epileptologist.

Currently, there is no reliable data on the increased incidence of pregnancy complications (pre-eclampsia, arterial hypertension, spontaneous abortion, seizure frequency changes, status epilepticus) in epileptic women taking AEDs compared to the general population.

Minimal effective doses of AEDs should be used during pregnancy, preferably in monotherapy [1]. Taking a single drug reduces the risk of possible foetal defects. The dose of AEDs should be as low as possible, but such a dose should not cause generalised seizures. Changing the drug to an analogue may lead to an increase in the frequency of seizures. It is recommended to continue taking the same drug from the same manufacturer.

An important safety factor is the use of preparations with controlled release of the active substance, which can be used 2 times a day. This allows to exclude concentration peaks, especially unfavourable for the foetus. Nausea and vomiting in toxicosis can significantly complicate the administration of AEDs. To avoid decreased blood concentrations of drugs, intravenous or rectal forms can be used. In case of frequent vomiting (up to 20 or more times a day), hospitalisation is indicated. Unfortunately, none of the "first aid drugs for attacks" are registered in Russia. The only available way to prevent a seizure in Russian conditions is the use of diazepam tablets under the tongue at the premonition of seizures. Taking additional doses of AEDs, as a rule, does not make sense, because the absorption period is quite long.

Psychotropic drugs and strong sleeping pills are contraindicated in pregnant women. Sleep disorders should be treated with non-medication methods: phytotherapy (decoction of aira, ivan-tea, oregano, chamomile, mint, linden, peony, etc.); psychotherapy (listening to soft relaxing music before bedtime); aromatherapy; observance of sleep hygiene, as well as labour and rest regime.

Fluoroquinolones are contraindicated in epilepsy. The use of some other groups of antibiotics and antimicrobials: macrolides, high doses of penicillins should also be avoided if possible. However, if there is inflammation, the benefit of antibiotic therapy may outweigh the risk.

Head and neck physiotherapy is contraindicated in pregnant women with epilepsy.

Taking valproate is associated with an increase in body weight. However, weight gain also occurs in pregnancy. In most cases, it is not possible to say definitively whether weight gain is due to valproate use or to the abnormal course of pregnancy. To correct weight gain, observation by a gynaecologist-endocrinologist and dieting are indicated. Replacement of valproate with another AED during pregnancy is not justified, may lead to the appearance/increase of seizures and is acceptable only in case of extreme necessity.

Seizure frequency may increase in 15-20% of women, more often in the first or third trimester of pregnancy. An increase in seizure frequency cannot be predicted on the basis of seizure type, duration of epilepsy, or seizure frequency in a previous pregnancy. Even the presence of hormone-dependent epilepsy is not a predictor of increased seizure frequency during pregnancy. Seizure recurrence may be due to the pharmacokinetics of AEDs during pregnancy.

The most frequent provocateurs of seizures during pregnancy are emotional stress and sleep deprivation. Increased body temperature can provoke seizures and accelerate the excretion of AEDs. Hypoglycaemia (lower blood glucose levels) and alcohol consumption can also lead to the onset/increase of seizures. Seizures may become more frequent after a brain injury. Therefore, it is necessary to lead a proper lifestyle, carefully monitor the state of health, observe the regime of labour and rest. However, quite often attacks occur quite unpredictably, and a "healthy lifestyle" does not allow you to prevent them. Therefore, it is necessary to take a sufficient dose of AEDs, not only to eliminate provoking factors.

Severe and moderate forms of ARVI or influenza aggravate the course of epilepsy and can provoke the appearance/incidence of seizures. Despite this, specific prophylaxis (vaccination) is not recommended because, firstly, the effect of some vaccines on the foetus has not been adequately studied, which means that they are potentially dangerous for the foetus, and secondly, the adverse reaction to their administration is fever. To prevent influenza in pregnant women use natural immunomodulators ("folk remedies"), as well as hygienic measures (avoid crowded places, wash hands and face, rinse nose and eyes after returning from the street).

Generalised convulsive seizures are considered the most dangerous for both mother and child. When they develop, many factors have a negative impact on the body of the mother and child. Focal seizures can

be conditionally considered to have no effect, but it is important to remember that they can take a generalised form.

The study of the concentration of AEDs in the blood during pregnancy should be carried out repeatedly, at least once every 2 months, and in case of recurrent attacks - monthly. This should be done not only because in the course of pregnancy there may be changes in AED metabolism or drug concentration due to weight gain, but also to monitor compliance.

The plasma concentration of lamotrigine can decrease significantly during pregnancy. Also at the end of the first trimester, it may be necessary to increase the daily dosage of levetiracetam due to increased clearance.

To assess the full functioning of the placenta and early diagnosis of fetoplacental insufficiency, it is advisable to study the hormones of the fetoplacental complex (placental lactogen, progesterone, estriol, cortisol) monthly from the end of the first trimester of pregnancy.

Special attention is paid to the study of alpha-fetoprotein. At the end of the last century it was found that in neural tube defects in the foetus (anencephaly and vertebral cleft) in the serum of the mother increases the content of alpha-fetoprotein, a protein that is synthesised in the liver of the foetus. In neural tube defects, alpha-fetoprotein penetrates through the capillary wall in the area of the defect into the amniotic fluid and from there into the mother's bloodstream. With the introduction into clinical practice of the method of determining the level of alpha-fetoprotein in maternal serum, it was possible to improve the accuracy of diagnosis of neural tube defects in the foetus. Thus, this method is used to detect up to 97-98% of cases of anencephaly. Determination of serum alpha-fetoprotein levels is also used to diagnose multiple pregnancies, defects of the anterior abdominal wall and other foetal malformations. It has been found that in Down syndrome in the fetus, the content of alpha-fetoprotein in the serum of the mother decreases. Determination of alpha-fetoprotein levels are carried out at 15-20 weeks of pregnancy, the most informative study at 16-18 weeks, it is repeated when changes in ultrasound.

Ultrasound examination of the foetus is carried out at 19-21 weeks of pregnancy to exclude developmental anomalies. High levels of alpha-fetoprotein in the serum of the mother is an absolute indication for ultrasound of the foetus.

Cardiotocography is an important diagnostic method. This method provides more objective information about the fetal cardiovascular system than auscultation of the heartbeat. Cardiotocography evaluates the fetal heart rate, its variability, the presence of accelerations (increase in heart rate by 15-25 beats per minute during fetal movements) and decelerations (reduction of heart rate by no more than 30 seconds during labour). A normal foetus has a heart rate of 120-160 beats per minute, good heart rate variability (mainly due to accelerations) and no high-amplitude decelerations. The value of this method lies in the simultaneous detection of fetal heartbeats and uterine motility. The method allows the diagnosis of intrauterine fetal hypoxia due to fetoplacental insufficiency.

The patient should warn the obstetrician that a number of drugs are contraindicated: nootropics, analeptics, psychotropic drugs (except for split-dose administration of low-dose benzodiazepines to potentiate analgesia in labour).

Due to the potential possibility of vitamin K deficiency when taking enzyme-inducing AEDs (carbamazepine) in the last weeks of pregnancy, it is advisable to prescribe vitamin K at a dose of 10-15 mg/day to a woman using these AEDs.

Peculiarities of the labour period in women with epilepsy

Women with epilepsy have a higher risk of haemorrhage, weakness of labour and pre-eclampsia (the risk of the latter is 2 times higher than in the general population), placental abruption, preterm labour, and are twice as likely to be delivered by vacuum extraction or caesarean section. Full seizure control is essential to reduce the risk of complications.

The likelihood of an epileptic seizure during labour and within 24 h after delivery is higher than the likelihood of an epileptic seizure during other periods of pregnancy. This is primarily due to missed administration of AEDs. Epilepsy is not a contraindication for natural delivery, and the medication management and anaesthesia do not differ

from generally accepted standards. In most cases, prolonged epidural analgesia is possible.

Indications for caesarean section are increased frequency of epileptic seizures, seizures more than once a week in the last trimester of pregnancy, serial or status epilepticus in the prenatal period, foetal hypoxia, weakness of labour, seizure during labour.

Management of the postpartum period in women with epilepsy

The patient should be warned about the need to carefully follow the AED regimen during this period, as there is a risk of decompensation of epilepsy in the postpartum period due to physical overexertion, stress, increased drug load, increased estrogen activity.

Also after delivery, symptoms of AED overdose may occur due to decreased body weight of a woman in labour, blood loss in labour, metabolic changes. In case of symptoms of neurotoxicity - somnolence, diplopia, nystagmus, ataxia, it is necessary to urgently study the concentration of AED in blood. If the dosage of the drug was increased during pregnancy, it is advisable to return to the daily dose used before pregnancy. If the mother has no seizures and the child has no side effects of AEDs, it is not advisable to change the dose. Another danger lies in the increase in the frequency of seizures due to childcare, night wakings.

Breastfeeding a newborn is quite possible, because the dose of AEDs entering the baby's body with milk is incomparable with the amount of the drug entering the fetus through the placenta. An exception should be made for phenobarbital and lamotrigine. The mechanisms of their excretion from the newborn organism are unformed, which may lead to drug accumulation [1].

AEDs acted on the foetus throughout pregnancy, and their content in breast milk is significantly lower than in the blood of the pregnant woman. In addition, it is possible to reduce the amount of drug in milk by taking AEDs after breastfeeding.

The most frequent complication in newborns is skin manifestations in the form of allergic reactions. Cases of haemorrhagic complications (increased bleeding) have been described. The use of phenobarbital during pregnancy can lead to both sedation (drowsiness, weak suckling, muscle weakness, lethargy, lethargy, lethargy) and withdrawal syndrome (motor agitation, restless sleep, frequent crying without reason), if for any reason breastfeeding is stopped.

If the newborn has low activity, lethargy during feeding, gastrointestinal disorders and other symptoms suspicious of intoxication, it is better to switch to artificial feeding.

Determining the concentration of the drug in breast milk is of no practical use. Much more important is the presence of clinical manifestations of AED effects in the child. The dose of the drug that reaches the child with breast milk depends on the amount of milk sucked. In children over 6 months of age who have already been given complementary foods, the dose of the drug is reduced as the child grows.

For children at high risk of seizures, prophylactic vaccinations are withheld. Vaccination is undesirable in the acute phase of infectious diseases accompanied by fever. Scheduled vaccination is postponed until the acute manifestations of the disease are over. Possible withdrawal from DPT vaccination or its replacement with DPTM.

Women with epilepsy should breastfeed lying in bed or sitting on the floor, preferably in the presence of relatives. This will minimise the risk of injury to the mother and/or baby during a seizure.

Preeclampsia and eclampsia in female patients with epilepsy

Eclampsia is considered a condition characterised by the development of one or more generalised seizures in a woman with preeclampsia. In half of the cases, eclampsia develops before delivery; the incidence is about the same during labour and in the postpartum period.

Preeclampsia is characterised by arterial hypertension with proteinuria and oedema in the second half of pregnancy. The diagnosis of severe pre-eclampsia is made in the presence of one of the following criteria:

An increase in systolic BP more than 160 mmHg or diastolic BP more than 110 mmHg, recorded twice with an interval of more than 6 h;

loss of protein with urine more than 5 g/day or a strongly positive result of rapid urine protein analysis;

oliguria (urine volume below 400 ml/day);

severe headache (due to brain oedema) or visual disturbance (due to retinal oedema or spasm of retinal arteries);

signs of pulmonary oedema and cyanosis.

Severe pre-eclampsia is an indication for immediate delivery. Seizures in eclampsia should be regarded as provoked, arising against the background of acute brain damage. Encephalopathy in eclampsia develops due to impaired autoregulation of cerebral blood flow and increased capillary permeability. This leads to cerebral oedema, development of multiple microhaemorrhages and disseminated intravascular coagulation, which is the cause of seizures. The risk of eclampsia is not always proportional to the severity of arterial hypertension. In young first-time mothers with baseline arterial hypotension, eclampsia can occur at an average BP of 120-130 mmHg. Therefore, effective hypotensive therapy is required in all cases of pre-eclampsia, despite the fact that it does not significantly affect the transition to eclampsia. Among hypotensive drugs, vasodilators should not be prescribed, as they have the ability to increase the increase in cerebral perfusion oedema.

Another area of therapy is seizure control. In the past, benzodiazepines and phenytoin were used to control seizures. Currently, magnesium sulfate solution is considered the most effective remedy. As a prophylactic agent for severe pre-eclampsia in the antenatal period, magnesium sulfate can be administered intramuscularly, in the presence of seizures - intravenously. The drug is administered intravenously slowly in a dose of 4 g (16 ml of 25% solution), and then - 1 g (4 ml of 25% solution) every hour for a day. In the first day it may be necessary to administer an additional 2-4 g of magnesium sulphate if the attacks continue. In the future, the drug is switched to intramuscular administration.

During therapy, the level of urine excretion (more than 100 ml/h), frequency of respiratory movements (more than 12 per min) and preservation of tendon reflexes are monitored. Changes in these parameters indicate the toxic effect of magnesium sulfate. To correct the dosage use intravenous jet injection of 10 ml of 10% solution of calcium gluconate. Calcium channel blockers (nifedipine) should not be administered together with magnesium sulfate due to common mechanisms of action of these drugs.

There is no consensus on which AED is the safest.

Taking AEDs during pregnancy is vital, because even in the case of full control of seizures, lifestyle changes, water-salt imbalance, metabolic changes, weight gain, maternal-fetal interaction, hormonal changes and other factors increase the risk of recurrence of seizures well controlled before pregnancy. Of particular concern is the risk of maternal tonic-clonic seizures, which can lead to significant adverse fetal health consequences, including intracranial haemorrhage, transient bradycardia and heartbeat disturbances [2]. When prescribing antiepileptic therapy to women of high childbearing potential, the possible teratogenic effect of AEDs should be taken into account. Statistical analysis shows that AED monotherapy doubles the risk of major congenital malformations and polytherapy triples it [3]. On the other hand, the course of pregnancy in women with epilepsy is quite diverse, with the majority of children being born without structural or behavioural abnormalities. Thus, the question of the possibility and necessity of AED cancellation at this stage remains controversial.

We present data on the teratogenic effect of the most studied AEDs. Some observations failed to reveal a reliable increase in the risk of malformations under the influence of carbamazepine [4, 5]. In contrast, other studies have shown that carbamazepine use during pregnancy is associated with an increased risk of major malformations in unexposed offspring [6]. Hernandez-Diaz et al found a 24-fold increase in the incidence of orofacial clefts when taking carbamazepine [7]. The risk of cardiac anomalies increases [8].

The effects of lamotrigine, levetiracetam and topiramate on the foetus are also poorly understood. There is evidence that intrauterine exposure to lamotrigine and topiramate may increase the risk of craniofacial defects [9, 10], but the sample size is too small for such conclusions.

Valproic acid causes a significant dose-dependent increase in the risk of anatomical and behavioural teratogenic effects in the developing fetus. The risk of malformations is thought to increase at doses of 600

mg/day and is most significant at doses greater than 1000 mg/day, although, as with all AEDs, individual susceptibility plays a role [3].

A significant factor reducing the teratogenic risk of AEDs is the use of folic acid preparations by a woman in the first trimester of pregnancy. Carbamazepine reduces its concentration in the blood, while the deficiency of this vitamin is a risk factor for major anomalies of central nervous system development.

To reduce the risk of AED-induced congenital anomalies of the foetus it is advisable to plan pregnancy, if possible - to prescribe AEDs with minimal teratogenic aggressiveness (carbamazepine, lamotrigine at a dose of up to 200 mg/day) to women of childbearing age, to use minimally effective doses of drugs and monotherapy regimes, to prescribe folic acid at a dose of 3-5 mg/day several months before the planned conception and in the first trimester of pregnancy. However, the choice of AEDs should always be guided by general rules: the choice should be made strictly in accordance with the form of epilepsy and the type of seizures from the AED of first choice for this form of the disease,

because the aggressive course of epilepsy during pregnancy due to inadequate treatment is no less dangerous than the teratogenic risk, and carries a threat to the well-being not only of the mother, but also of the developing foetus.

The actions of physicians and women with epilepsy associated with the fear of teratogenic effects

Conclusions: Thus, the actions of physicians and women with epilepsy associated with the fear of teratogenic effects of AEDs are often dangerous and can lead to serious consequences. In particular, it is inadmissible to reduce effective doses of AEDs or to cancel antiepileptic therapy on the basis of such motivations, to change an effective AED for a less effective but safer one. This may lead to the development of severe decompensation of the disease up to status epilepticus. To reduce effective doses of AEDs or to cancel antiepileptic therapy on the basis of such motivations, to change an effective AED for a less effective but safer one. This may lead to the development of severe decompensation of the disease up to status epilepticus.

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ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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